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**Inhibition of *Quorum Sensing* (QS) in *Yersinia enterocolitica* by an Orange Extract Rich
in Glycosylated Flavanones**

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12 **ABSTRACT**

13 Flavanones, flavonoids abundant in *Citrus*, have been shown to interfere with *Quorum*
14 *Sensing* (*QS*) and affect related physiological processes. We have investigated the *QS*-
15 inhibitory effects of an orange extract enriched in *O*-glycosylated flavanones (mainly
16 naringin, neohesperidin and hesperidin). The *QS*-inhibitory capacity of this extract and its
17 main flavanone components was first screened using the bacteriological monitoring system
18 *Chromobacterium violaceum*. We next examined the ability of the orange extract and of some
19 of the flavanones to: i) reduce the levels of the *QS*-mediators produced by *Y. enterocolitica*
20 using HPLC-MS/MS, ii) inhibit biofilm formation and iii) inhibit swimming and swarming
21 motility. Additionally, we evaluated changes in the expression of specific genes involved in
22 the synthesis of the lactones (*yenI*, *yenR*) and in the flagellar regulon (*flhDC*, *fleB*, *fliA*) by
23 RT-PCR. The results showed that the orange extract and its main flavanone components
24 inhibited *QS* in *C. violaceum*, diminished the levels of lactones secreted by *Y. enterocolitica*
25 to the media and decreased *QS*-associated biofilm maturation without affecting bacterial
26 growth. Amongst the tested compounds, naringin was found to inhibit swimming motility.
27 Exposure to the orange extract and (or) to naringin was also found to be associated with
28 induction of the transcription levels of *yenR*, *flhDC* and *fliA*. This work shows the in vitro *QS*-
29 inhibitory effects of an orange extract enriched in flavanones against a human enteropathogen
30 at doses that can be achieved through the diet and suggests that consumption of these natural
31 extracts may have a beneficial antipathogenic effect.

32

33 *Keywords:* Cell-cell communication; Citrus polyphenols; flavonoids anti-*QS* activity; quorum
34 quenching; LC-MS/MS spectrometry; swimming; swarming; pathogenic bacteria; gene
35 expression.

36

37 INTRODUCTION

38 Phenolic compounds extracted from medicinal and dietary plants are believed to have a
39 range of beneficial effects against human chronic diseases such as cardiovascular diseases and
40 inflammation. ¹ A representative group of phenolic compounds are flavonoids, consisting of
41 different subgroups of compounds such as flavones, flavonols, flavanones, flavan-3-ols and
42 isoflavones. Citrus fruits are the main source of flavanones in the diet where they are present
43 principally in the glycoside form. The more abundant flavanones glycosides in citrus fruits are
44 hesperidin (hesperetin-7-*O*-rutinoside) and naringin (naringenin-7-*O*-neohesperidoside) with
45 concentrations ranging from 200 to 590 mg/L and from 16 to 84 mg/L in orange juice,
46 respectively ². Hesperidin and naringin are poorly absorbed since the glycoside group can
47 only be hydrolyzed in the distal part of the intestine. ³ Therefore, these flavanone glycosides
48 can reach the colon in their intact molecular form and may exert some effects on the
49 microorganisms present in the distal part of the intestine ^{4,5}. Recently, several studies have
50 demonstrated that certain flavonoids can act as inhibitors of the virulence of pathogenic
51 bacteria by interfering with *Quorum Sensing* (*QS*) mechanisms ^{6,7}. *QS* is a regulatory
52 mechanism which enables bacteria to make collective decisions with respect to the expression
53 of a specific set of genes. It has been demonstrated that *QS* mechanisms amplify bacterial
54 virulence by stimulating the expression of disease causing attributes, such as motility, biofilm
55 formation and secretion of virulence factors ⁸.

56 The genus *Yersinia* comprises human-pathogenic species such as the enteropathogenic
57 *Yersinia enterocolitica*. This pathogenic bacterium is a gammaproteobacterium that colonizes
58 the small intestine and can cause gastrointestinal distress as well as septicemia in
59 immunocompromised patients ⁹. *Y. enterocolitica* uses *N*-acyl homoserine lactones (AHLs) as
60 *QS* signal molecules to coordinate the expression of a battery of genes ¹⁰. The synthesis of
61 AHLs by *Y. enterocolitica* is regulated by a gene encoding an AHL synthase (*yenI*) and a

62 gene encoding a transcriptional activator named *yenR*¹¹. The *QS* systems of *Y. enterocolitica*
63 are also involved in the regulation of three major flagellar gene classes that control swimming
64 and swarming motility¹². Swarming motility is a flagellum-dependent behaviour that
65 facilitates bacterial migration over solid surfaces and is distinct from swimming motility,
66 which occurs in fluid environments¹³. It is well established that bacterial biofilms play an
67 important role in the pathogenesis of many human infections and increase bacterial resistance
68 to antimicrobial agents¹⁴. Many studies have suggested that *QS* can play an important role in
69 the formation of fully developed mature biofilms in several bacteria^{15, 16}.

70 In view of the important role of the *QS* mechanisms in the regulation of different
71 virulence factors such as motility and biofilm formation, the inhibition of *QS* systems is
72 considered a potential way to reduce the virulence of pathogenic bacteria^{7, 17, 18}. In previous
73 studies, citrus flavonoids have been reported to efficiently inhibit *QS* mechanisms, cell–cell
74 signaling and biofilm formation in *Vibrio harveyi* and *Escherichia coli* O157:H7¹⁹. These
75 authors also demonstrated that some flavonoids altered the expression of genes encoding the
76 type three secretion system in *V. harveyi*. In agreement with these results, Vandeputte et al.²⁰
77 also showed that naringenin, a citrus flavonoid, dramatically reduced the production of AHLs
78 *N*-(3-oxododecanoyl)-L-homoserine lactone (3-oxo-C12-HSL) and *N*-butanoyl-L-homoserine
79 lactone (C4-HSL) as well as the expression of several *QS*-related genes (i.e. *lasI*, *lasR*, *rhlI*,
80 *rhlR*, *lasA*, *lasB*, *phzA1* and *rhlA*) in *P. aeruginosa* PAO1.²⁰ In the search for natural products
81 that may act as *QS* inhibitors, we investigated the capacity of an orange extract rich in
82 flavanones to inhibit the production of AHLs, as well as *QS*-controlled biofilm formation and
83 motility in the pathogenic bacteria *Y. enterocolitica*. Additionally, some of the molecular
84 changes associated to the exposure of *Y. enterocolitica* to the orange extract or naringin were
85 also evaluated.

86

87 MATERIALS AND METHODS

88 **Materials.** Naringin (naringenin-7-*O*-neohesperidoside), neohesperidin (hesperetin-7-
89 neohesperidoside), hesperidin (hesperetin-7-*O*-rutinoside) and a soluble extract from bitter
90 orange were all kindly provided by Zoster S.A. (Murcia, Spain). Naringenin (4',5,7-
91 trihydroxyflavanone) was from Sigma Aldrich (Sigma Chemical, St. Louis, MO, USA) and
92 cinnamaldehyde from Extrasynthèse (Genay, France). The extract comprised of
93 approximately 42.1% soluble flavanones (% of the powder extract) with one most abundant
94 compound, naringin ($24.5 \pm 2.6\%$), followed by neohesperidin ($11.4 \pm 0.8\%$), hesperidin (1.7
95 $\pm 0.4\%$), naringenin ($0.4 \pm 0.1\%$), hesperetin ($0.4 \pm 0.1\%$) and isosakuranetin ($0.2 \pm 0.1\%$)⁵.
96 The structures of the three main flavanone constituents of the orange extract are shown in
97 **Figure 1**. The extract (a hygroscopic brown powder, 2.1% humidity), was kept in a tightly
98 closed container within a desiccator at room temperature and fresh stock solutions were
99 prepared by dissolving 0.1 g of the powder extract in 50 mL of water. Dilutions of the stock
100 solution were added to the cultures to obtain the final experimental concentrations stated for
101 each assay. Controls were always treated with the equivalent amount of water. Stock solutions
102 of the individual flavanones and cinnamaldehyde were prepared in DMSO, diluted and added
103 to the cultures to obtain the final experimental concentrations stated for each assay. Controls
104 were always treated with the equivalent amount of DMSO ($< 0.1\%$). Pure commercially
105 available *N*-hexanoyl-DL-homoserine lactone (C6-HSL, $\geq 97\%$, HPLC) and *N*-(3-oxo-
106 hexanoyl)-DL-homoserine lactone (3-oxo-C6-HSL, $\geq 97\%$, HPLC) were obtained from Sigma
107 (St. Louis, MO, USA) and dissolved in water. All other chemicals were of analytical / HPLC
108 grade. Ultrapure Millipore water (Millipore Corp., Massachusetts, USA) was used for all
109 solutions.
110

111 **Bacterial strains, culture conditions and growth.** *Yersinia enterocolitica* subsp.
112 *enterocolitica* (CECT 4315) and *Chromobacterium violaceum* (CECT 494) were obtained
113 from the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT, Valencia, Spain). Stocks of the strains
114 were stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in Luria-Bertani broth (LB broth Miller) (Scharlau Chemie S.A.,
115 Barcelona, Spain) supplemented with 30% glycerol. Unless otherwise stated, working
116 cultures of both strains were routinely grown in LB broth at $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under aerobic conditions
117 with shaking for 24 h. The pH of the cultures was 6.92-6.99 and was monitored using a
118 calibrated Crison MicropH 2000 pH meter (Crison Instruments S.A., Barcelona, Spain).

119 For bacterial growth analyses, diluted cultures of *Y. enterocolitica* were grown in sterile
120 96-well microtiter plates as previously described ²¹. The culture conditions were as indicated
121 above with a final volume of 200 μL per well. Plates were incubated at $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the
122 absence or presence of the test compounds with intermittent shaking and the OD₆₀₀ measured
123 hourly for 48 h using an Infinite M200 microplate reader (Tecan, Grödig, Austria).

124

125 ***C. violaceum* assay.** To evaluate the QS inhibitory capacity of the orange extract and of
126 its main flavanone components (naringin, neohesperidin and hesperidin) we first measured the
127 inhibition of the production of violacein using the biosensor strain *C. violaceum* as previously
128 described ²². Working solutions of the orange extract and of each individual flavanone were
129 filtered through a sterile Millex-GP 0.22 μm filter (Millipore Corp., Massachusetts, USA) and
130 added to the culture medium at the final concentrations of 100, 200 and 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (as
131 confirmed by LC-MS/MS analysis). Ten milliliters of LB broth were inoculated with 10 μL of
132 a working culture of *C. violaceum* and incubated with each of the concentrations of the extract
133 or the flavanones for 24 h. Then, 1 mL of culture was centrifuged at $19,314\times g$ for 10 min to
134 precipitate the insoluble violacein. The culture supernatant was discarded and 1 mL of DMSO
135 was added to the pellet. The solution was vortexed vigorously for 30 s to completely

136 solubilize violacein and centrifuged at $19,314\times g$ for 10 min to remove the cells. The violacein
137 was quantified at OD_{585} using a UV-1603 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Tokyo, Japan).

138

139 **Analysis of the AHLs produced by *Y. enterocolitica* using LC-MS/MS.** To assess the
140 specific inhibitory effect of the orange extract or of the flavanones on the levels of each of the
141 two main AHLs produced by *Y. enterocolitica*, 50 mL of LB were inoculated with 100 μ L of
142 a bacteria working culture in the absence and presence of the test compounds (at 200 μ g/mL)
143 and incubated at 30 °C for 48 h. We additionally tested a combination of naringin and
144 neohesperidin (49 μ g/mL and 22.8 μ g/mL, respectively) to investigate a possible synergistic
145 effect between these two most abundant flavanones in the extract. After incubation, bacterial
146 cells were removed by centrifugation at $9,632\times g$ at 4 °C for 15 min and the supernatants were
147 filtered through a Millex-GP 0.22 μ m filter (Millipore Corp., Massachusetts, USA). The cell-
148 free culture supernatants were extracted ($\times 2$) with 50 mL of acidified ethyl acetate (0.5%
149 formic acid). The organic phase was evaporated under reduced pressure at 35 °C and the
150 residue reconstituted in 2 mL of methanol. Methanol was removed in a Speedvac[®] SPD 121P
151 concentrator (Thermo Savant, Waltham, MA, USA) and the residue re-dissolved in 400 μ L of
152 methanol, filtered through a Millex-HV₁₃ 0.45 μ m filter (Millipore Corp., Massachusetts,
153 USA) and stored at -20 °C prior to analysis by LC-MS/MS.

154 To further investigate a putative direct chemical interaction between the orange extract
155 or each of the flavanones with the AHLs, we also measured the levels of C6-HSL and 3-oxo-
156 C6-HSL in the culture media after incubation for 48 h of known concentrations of the AHLs
157 (50 nM, 10 ng/mL) with the orange extract (200 μ g/mL) equivalent to 49 μ g/mL of naringin
158 (84.5 μ M), 22.8 μ g/mL of neohesperidin (37.0 μ M) and 3.4 μ g/mL of hesperidin (5.6 μ M) or
159 each single flavanone (at the same concentration present in the extract) in the absence of *Y.*

160 *enterocolitica*. Culture media was extracted and filtered as above prior to LC-MS/MS
161 analysis.

162 The levels of the AHLs were measured using LC-MS/MS following a method
163 previously described ²³ and further optimized for the specific analysis and relative
164 quantification of C6-HSL and 3-oxo-C6-HSL in the culture media of several bacteria
165 including *Y. enterocolitica* ²². Briefly, the peaks corresponding to C6-HSL and 3-oxo-C6-HSL
166 were identified based on their MS/MS fragmentation ion products and on the retention times
167 of commercial standards for each lactone. We selected the area of the characteristic single ion
168 *m/z* 102 to quantitate each AHL because of its specificity and better signal-to-noise ratio. The
169 specific use of the extracted ion chromatograms (EIC) for area calculation and quantification
170 reduces the possibility of misinterpreting overlapping peaks. Samples were injected and
171 analysed in the same day and run under the same conditions to avoid the influence of the
172 ionization fluctuation of the equipment. This method allows for relative quantification without
173 the need for a standard curve. Results are presented as the % of inhibition with respect to the
174 quantity of AHLs in the control samples (without test compounds).

175
176 **Biofilm formation.** The effects of the orange extract and its main flavanone
177 components on the formation of biofilm by *Y. enterocolitica* were evaluated using the crystal
178 violet assay ¹⁵ with some modifications ²². A number of wells of a sterile round-bottom 96-
179 well polystyrene plate (Nalge Nunc International, Rochester, NY, USA) containing 160 μ L of
180 LB broth and 20 μ L of the orange extract or each of the flavanones (200 μ g/mL final
181 concentration) were inoculated with 20 μ L of a working culture of *Y. enterocolitica* diluted
182 (1:100) in buffered peptone water (Scharlau Chemie S.A., Barcelona, Spain). Control wells
183 (without the test compounds) contained 160 μ L of LB broth, 20 μ L of sterile water or an
184 equivalent amount of DMSO (< 0.1%) and 20 μ L of a working culture of *Y. enterocolitica*.

185 After 24 h of incubation the wells were emptied and washed with sterile water ($\times 3$). The
186 biofilm layer formed on the wall of the wells was fixed with 200 μL of acidified methanol
187 (33% acetic acid), stained with crystal violet (0.1%) for 30 min, washed ($\times 4$) to eliminate
188 unbound dye and quantitated after solubilization of the crystal violet with 200 μL of 95%
189 ethanol by measuring the OD_{570} using a spectrophotometer (Synoptics, Cambridge, UK).
190 Background absorbance was determined in wells containing only sterile medium (160 μL)
191 and distilled water (40 μL). Naringenin and cinnamaldehyde were used as positive controls ¹⁹,
192 ²⁴.

193

194 **Motility.** The bacterial motility was determined at 25 °C following a previously
195 published method ¹³ with some modifications. Swimming and swarming motility were tested
196 using the same growth medium containing 1% tryptone and 10 mM glucose supplemented
197 with 0.30% Bacto agar (Difco, Detroit, MI, USA) for swimming and 0.35% Bacto agar for
198 swarming. For the swarming assays, agar plates were point-inoculated in the centre of each
199 plate without penetrating the agar surface, while in the case of the swimming tests, the
200 inoculum was stabbed into the medium with 1 μL of a working culture of *Y. enterocolitica*
201 and incubated in the absence and presence of the soluble orange extract or each flavanone at
202 25 °C for 24 h. At the end of the incubation period, the swimming and swarming migration
203 distances were calculated using a contrast camera imaging system (Synoptics, Cambridge,
204 UK). Cinnamaldehyde was included as a positive control ²⁴.

205

206 **Bacterial RNA extraction.** For the analysis of gene expression changes associated to
207 AHLs synthesis, bacteria were grown at 30 °C. For the analysis of gene expression changes in
208 members of the flagellar regulon, bacterial cells were grown at 25 °C. Samples from control
209 and treated cultures (at the concentrations stated) were taken at three different time points of

210 the bacterial growth curve (6, 14 and 24 h). Total RNA was extracted using the
211 MICROBexpress kit (Applied Biosystem, Foster City, USA) according to the manufacturer's
212 instructions. The purity and concentration of the samples were checked measuring the
213 absorbance at 260 and 280 nm using the Nanoquant plate in an Infinite M200 microplate
214 reader (Tecan, Grodig, Austria). Only RNA samples with an Abs₂₆₀/Abs₂₈₀ ratio between 2
215 and 2.2 were used for gene expression analyses.

216

217 **Gene expression analyses.** Two genes expressed in *Y. enterocolitica* and reported to be
218 involved in the synthesis of AHLs (*yenI*, *yenR*) and three members of the flagellar regulon
219 system (*fliA*, *fleB* and *flhDC*) were selected for the study ^{12, 13, 25}. Primers and probes were
220 designed based on their coding sequences using the Custom Assay Design Tool (Taqman
221 system) (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, USA) (**Table 1**). Relative expression was measured
222 by one-step quantitative RT-PCR Taqman system (Applied Biosystems, Madrid, Spain) run
223 on the ABI 7500 system following manufacturer's conditions, using a total reaction volume of
224 25 µL in a MicroAmp Optical 96-well plate covered by optical adhesive covers and using
225 Taqman Universal Master Mix (Applied Biosystems, Madrid, Spain). The expression levels
226 of each gene were normalized to the levels of the housekeeping gene *16S rRNA* utilizing a
227 standard curve method for relative quantification.

228

229 **Statistical Analysis.** Results of the phenotypic bacterial responses are presented as the
230 mean values ± SD of three independent experiments with at least two replicates per
231 experiment. Gene expression analyses were carried out in at least four biological replicates
232 and RT-PCR assays consisted of three technical replicates run under identical conditions.
233 Statistical analyses were performed using PASW Statistics 18 for Windows (SPSS Inc.,
234 Chicago, IL, USA). The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test showed agreement of the empirical

235 distribution of the data with normality assumption. The Levene's test was used to assess the
236 equality of variances and statistical differences between experimental groups were determined
237 by the unpaired Student's *t* test, using two-tailed and $P<0.05$ or $P<0.01$ as the level of
238 significance.

239

240 RESULTS

241 ***Quorum Sensing (QS) inhibition by the orange extract and its main flavanone***
242 **components using a biosensor strain.** The capacity of the orange extract and of naringin,
243 neohesperidin and hesperidin to reduce the production of violacein by *C. violaceum* is
244 presented in **Table 2**. Results show that the orange extract and each of the individual
245 flavanones caused a modest but significant inhibition of the production of violacein at the
246 three concentrations tested. With this bacterial model no significant differences were detected
247 between the inhibition caused by the extract and that caused by the tested flavanones except
248 for hesperidin that exhibited a slightly lower inhibitory activity at the two highest
249 concentrations tested (200 and 400 $\mu\text{g/mL}$).

250

251 **Effects of the orange extract and its main flavanone components on the levels of**
252 **AHLs produced by *Yersinia enterocolitica* using LC-MS/MS.** The putative anti-*QS* activity
253 of the orange extract, naringin, neohesperidin and hesperidin against *Y. enterocolitica* was
254 first examined by quantitating the effects of these compounds on the levels of AHLs produced
255 by these bacteria. LC-MS/MS analysis of the AHLs present in the bacterial culture
256 supernatants confirmed that the two major AHLs produced by *Y. enterocolitica* were 3-oxo-
257 C6HSL and C6HSL and that exposure to 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of the orange extract or of each of the
258 flavanones for 48 h caused a decrease in both peaks as shown in the chromatograms depicted
259 in **Figure 2**. Results expressed as % of inhibition with respect to the quantity of AHLs in the

260 control samples (without test compounds) are presented in **Figure 3**. These data corroborated
261 the *QS*-inhibitory effects detected with the *Chromobacterium* assay but unlike this method, a
262 significant difference was observed between the inhibitory effect of the complete extract
263 (68.5% and 64.4% for 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL, respectively) and that of the individual
264 flavanones (values between 24.2% and 36.5%). Exposure of *Y. enterocolitica* to a mixture of
265 naringin and neohesperidin at the concentrations present in the extract also showed that the
266 mixture of these two flavanones did not inhibited the production of 3-oxo-C6HSL (17.0%) or
267 C6HSL (20.4%) as much as the complete orange extract and discarded a synergistic effect
268 between these two main components of the extract. We cannot exclude that other components
269 of the extract may contribute to the observed inhibitory effect.

270 To exclude the possibility that the decrease in the levels of AHLs might have been
271 caused by some degradation and (or) transformation of the AHLs as a consequence of a direct
272 interaction of these molecules with the orange extract or the flavanones, we incubated known
273 concentrations of 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL in uninoculated broth supplemented or not with
274 the test compounds. Our results revealed that the orange extract, as well as the flavanones,
275 were able to slightly decrease the levels of 3-oxo-C6-HSL and C6-HSL in the absence of *Y.*
276 *enterocolitica*. Inhibition values were all in the range 2 to 10% of the total inhibition observed
277 in the presence of *Y. enterocolitica*. Overall, these data indicate that the anti-*QS* activity of the
278 orange extract and the flavanones against *Y. enterocolitica* may be, at least, partially caused
279 by an interference with the production of the autoinducer signals by the bacterium.

280

281 **Effect of the orange extract and naringin on the growth kinetic parameters of *Y.***
282 ***enterocolitica*.** To further ascertain that the observed anti-*QS* effects were not due to an
283 inhibitory effect on the bacterial growth, we next determined the growth kinetic parameters of
284 *Y. enterocolitica* following incubation with the orange extract or its main flavanone

285 component, naringin. The results (**Table 3**) showed that no significant changes were observed
286 in the maximum specific growth (μ_{max}) at the three concentrations tested. Moreover, there
287 were not significant differences in the maximum absorbance values attained at the stationary
288 phase (A) between the bacteria grown in culture media supplemented with the extract or
289 naringin and the control cultures. Equally, the lag phase duration was not significantly
290 affected by the addition of the orange extract or naringin. These results indicate that at the
291 three concentrations tested, the growth rate of *Y. enterocolitica* is not affected by the orange
292 extract or naringin and that therefore, the decrease observed in the concentration of the AHLs
293 cannot be attributed to any bactericidal or bacteriostatic effect on *Y. enterocolitica*. Based on
294 these results a 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ intermediate concentration was selected for further studies.

295

296 **Effect of the orange extract on *yenI* and *yenR* expression.** In an attempt to identify
297 some of the putative molecular changes that may be associated to the decrease in the
298 concentration of AHLs produced by *Y. enterocolitica*, we compared the expression levels of
299 specific genes involved in the synthesis (*yenI* and *yenR*) before and after exposure of the
300 bacteria to the orange extract (200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for 6, 14 and 24 h (**Figure 4**). Batch-to-batch
301 variability in the expression of these genes ('expression noise') has been reported to range
302 from 0.7 to 1.3²¹ and, therefore, only values above 1.3 or below 0.7 (shown in **Figure 4** by
303 dashed lines) were considered as indicators of upregulation or downregulation by the
304 treatment. RT-PCR analyses from at least four biological independent replicates revealed that
305 the expression of *yenI* was not altered following exposure of the bacterial cells to the extract.
306 However, treatment of the cells with the orange extract was associated to a small increase in
307 the expression of *yenR* more noticeable at 24 h (relative expression treated/control: 1.8 ± 1.4).
308 This increase was significant when compared to gene expression ratios at 6 h ($P < 0.05$).

309

310 **Inhibition of biofilm formation in *Y. enterocolitica* by the orange extract and its**
311 **main flavanones.** The inhibitory effects of the orange extract and its main flavanones (200
312 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) on the formation of biofilm by *Y. enterocolitica* are presented in **Figure 5**. Naringenin
313 ($95 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and cinnamaldehyde ($50 \mu\text{g/mL}$) were included as positive controls. Under the
314 conditions of our assay, these two compounds inhibited the formation of biofilm by $68.1 \pm$
315 6.7% and $60.0 \pm 10.7\%$, respectively. The formation of biofilm was also significantly reduced
316 by the extract and all the tested flavanones with inhibition mean values between 20 and 30%.
317 No significant differences were found, however, among the different compounds. Direct
318 addition of 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL ($20 \mu\text{g/mL}$ each) to the assay did not reverse the
319 inhibition induced by naringin, naringenin or cinnamaldehyde.

320

321 **Inhibition of motility in *Y. enterocolitica* by the orange extract and naringin.** We
322 next evaluated the effect of the orange extract and of naringin, neohesperidin, and hesperidin
323 (at 200 and $400 \mu\text{g/mL}$) on the motility of *Y. enterocolitica* by analyzing the effects of these
324 compounds on swimming and swarming at 25°C . None of the compounds tested had any
325 effect on swarming and only naringin exhibited a significant inhibitory effect on swimming at
326 $400 \mu\text{g/mL}$ ($46.0 \pm 10\%$; **Figure 6**). Cinnamaldehyde, which was included as a positive
327 control, also strongly inhibited swimming motility in *Y. enterocolitica* ($59.0 \pm 11.5\%$). Direct
328 addition of 3-oxo-C6HSL and C6HSL ($20 \mu\text{g/mL}$ each) to the assay did not reverse the
329 inhibition induced by naringin or cinnamaldehyde.

330

331 **Effect of the orange extract and naringin on *flhDC*, *fliA* and *fleB* expression.** We
332 first measured the expression changes for these three flagellar-related genes in control
333 cultures of *Y. enterocolitica* at 25°C and at three different time points of the bacterial growth
334 curve, 6, 14 and 24 h, which corresponded to the mid of the lag phase and the beginning of

335 the exponential and stationary phases (**Figure 7**). Results indicate that the mRNA levels of
336 these genes are slightly induced after 14 h and 24 h of growth.

337 Changes in the expression of these three genes after exposure to the orange extract or to
338 naringin are shown in **Figure 8** (values above 1.3 or below 0.7, 'expression noise', are
339 indicated by dashed lines). The most significant changes were found for *flhDC* which was
340 upregulated in *Y. enterocolitica* after exposure to 200 µg/mL and 400 µg/mL of orange extract
341 for 6 h (relative expression treated/control: 3.8 ± 2.9 and 2.4 ± 0.7 , respectively) and 24 h (2.7
342 ± 1.5 and 2.3 ± 0.7 , respectively) whereas at 14 h the levels of this transcript were within the
343 range of the expression noise values (**Figure 8A**). Similarly, exposure to naringin also caused
344 a significant induction in the expression of this gene at 6 h (3.4 ± 0.6 and 1.5 ± 1.2) and 24 h
345 (2.1 ± 0.8 and 1.5 ± 1.0) both at 200 µg/mL and 400 µg/mL of the flavanone, respectively
346 (**Figure 8D**). Although gene expression changes for *fliA* did not reach significance, ratios
347 were all above the limits of intrinsic variability indicating an apparent general up-regulation
348 of the expression of this gene after the treatments (**Figure 8B and 8B**). The expression of *fleB*
349 was slightly (although not significantly) upregulated following 14 h of exposure to the extract
350 (1.7 ± 0.5 at 400 µg/mL) or to the flavanone (1.9 ± 1.9 and 1.6 ± 1.4 at 200 and 400 µg/mL,
351 respectively) (**Figure 8C and 8F**). At 24 h, the expression of *fleB* was found to be
352 significantly downregulated by the orange extract (0.6 ± 0.1 , $P < 0.05$) at the highest
353 concentration tested (400 µg/mL).

354

355 **DISCUSSION**

356 The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention reported that ~60% of all infections in
357 developed countries are caused by biofilms, which are bacterial communities that settle and
358 proliferate on surfaces and are covered by an exopolymer matrix. A high proportion of
359 chronic infections, often untreatable, are accompanied by the formation of biofilms with a

360 high resistance to antibiotics ²⁶. In this context, the search for natural compounds able to
361 attenuate bacterial pathogenicity rather than bacterial growth has become a priority. Former
362 studies have shown that different fruit and vegetable extracts as well as some of their phenolic
363 components or derivatives are able to inhibit the synthesis of *QS* autoinducers and (or) to
364 attenuate *QS*-associated processes such as motility, biofilm formation or secretion of
365 virulence factors ^{6, 7, 15, 19-22, 27-30}. Recently, the anti-*QS* properties of several citrus flavonoids
366 against *E. coli*, *V. harveyi* and *P. aeruginosa* have been reported ^{19, 20}. In these studies, the
367 non-glycosylated flavanone naringenin (aglycone) has emerged as an efficient *QS* inhibitor.
368 However, in some citrus fruits such as oranges as well as in some of their derived products,
369 the main flavanone components are the *O*-glycosylated derivatives such as hesperidin and
370 naringin². In this study we show that a soluble orange extract as well as its main flavanone
371 components, the glycosides naringin, neohesperidin and hesperidin, exert a *QS*-inhibitory
372 effect against *Y. enterocolitica* as shown by a significant reduction in the levels of autoinducer
373 molecules (AHLs) produced by the bacteria and a significant inhibition of the formation of
374 biofilm. In addition, naringin was also able to inhibit the ability of *Y. enterocolitica* to swim
375 on agar plates.

376 Following a dietary approach, the intestinal pathogen *Y. enterocolitica* was exposed to
377 low doses of the extract or the flavanones (200 µg/mL, equivalent to ~320 – 350 µM). These
378 quantities are within the range of the levels that can be detected in the intestine even several
379 hours after oral intake of these compounds⁵. At these concentrations, the orange extract and
380 the individual flavanones moderately inhibited the formation of biofilm by *Y. enterocolitica*
381 (20-30%). Similar values can be found in the literature for these and other natural flavonoids
382 and citrus components. In the same way, naringin, neohesperidin and hesperidin at 100 µg/mL
383 inhibited the formation of biofilm in *E. coli* by approximately 50%, 40% and 5%,
384 respectively¹⁹. Also, several citrus limonoids at 100 µg/mL caused approximately between 20

385 and 35% inhibition of *E. coli* biofilm formation²⁹ or the flavonoid catechin, at concentrations
386 10 times higher (1000 µg/mL), inhibited biofilm formation in *P. aeruginosa* by only 45%³⁰.
387 The anti-*QS* effectiveness of the compounds can vary considerably not only depending on the
388 concentrations used but also on the bacterial species investigated. We have shown that
389 naringin can inhibit biofilm formation, motility and AHLs production in *Y. enterocolitica*,
390 however, this compound was not able to inhibit *QS*-controlled virulence factors in *P.*
391 *aeruginosa* (PAO1)²⁰. In a similar fashion, naringenin which efficiently inhibited the
392 formation of biofilm in *E. coli* and *V. harveyi* (approximately 70-90% inhibition at 100
393 µg/mL)¹⁹, was not able to inhibit the formation of biofilm by *Salmonella typhimurium* at
394 concentrations between 1.56 and 100 µg/mL. However, naringenin, at 200 µg/mL, induced
395 the formation of biofilm in these bacteria²⁸. Our data and others indicate that flavanones can
396 influence bacteria *QS*-related mechanisms in different ways depending on the type of bacterial
397 cells and on the concentration used.

398 Inhibition values between 20% and 40% may appear to be moderate or less significant
399 when compared to other more effective compounds that may cause inhibition values as high
400 as 90%³¹. However, it is not a trivial issue to establish whether an effect is ‘biologically
401 significant’, since this will depend on the specific biological effects investigated. From the
402 point of view of intestinal infections by pathogens such as *Y. enterocolitica*, modest effects by
403 dietary compounds may become relevant in the long term. As it has been repeatedly shown in
404 the field of polyphenols bioactivity, exposure of cultured cells or animal models to dietary
405 low levels of plant derived polyphenols causes, in general, very moderate effects in contrast to
406 treatment with high doses of xenobiotic compounds or drugs (pharmacological approach)³².
407 Our results suggest that regular consumption of µM concentrations of the orange extract or
408 the flavanones may exert moderate anti-*QS* effects in the gut.

409 Since the orange extract and its main flavanone components interfered with the *QS*
410 system in *Y. enterocolitica*, we hypothesised that this may be reflected at the transcription
411 level of *QS*-related genes. We first investigated the effect of the orange extract on the
412 expression levels of *yenI* and *yenR* which are involved in the synthesis of AHLs and its
413 regulation in *Y. enterocolitica*^{13, 25}. Our results exhibited a high variability probably caused by
414 ‘expression noise’ which includes ‘intrinsic noise’ driven by random fluctuations in mRNA
415 synthesis and degradation and ‘extrinsic noise’ which originates from external factors³³.
416 Previous studies reporting *QS*-gene expression changes associated to bacterial cell exposure
417 to flavonoids also showed a high variability in the results with Coefficient Variation values as
418 high as 45% in some cases²⁰. Regarding our experimental conditions, replicated bacterial
419 cultures in shake flasks have been reported to produce protein expression profiles more
420 variable than those bacteria cultivated under more controlled environments, i.e. bioreactors or
421 chemostats³⁴. To partially filter out some of this noise we had determined the variability in the
422 expression of the selected genes in control batches under our culture conditions²¹. Thus, gene
423 expression ratios between 0.7 and 1.3 were established as intrinsic noise and excluded from
424 the results. In general, results reported in the literature on *QS*-associated gene expression
425 regulation by exogenous phenolic compounds are still scarce and incomplete. Certain
426 flavonoids such as catechin or naringenin have been reported to inhibit *QS* and this inhibition
427 was associated to a downregulation in the expression levels of AHLs synthase and regulator
428 genes^{7, 20}. A closer view at the reported changes shows, however, that gene expression
429 regulation is clearly a time-dependent process and that results are markedly affected by the
430 time point at which gene expression is measured. Large differences in gene expression
431 changes have been shown even within 2 h¹⁹. The downregulation of *lasI* and *lasR* by catechin
432 and naringenin in *P. aeruginosa* was reported at 8 and 18 h of growth²⁰. Our data clearly
433 display a significant tendency to an induction in the expression of *yenR* following 24 h of

434 exposure to the orange extract (**Figure 4**). In agreement with these results, other phenolic
435 compounds such as urolithin-B, an ellagitannin derived metabolite, also inhibited the
436 production of AHLs in *Y. enterocolitica* but increased the mRNA levels of *yenR* after 24 h of
437 exposure²¹. Although we do not have a clear explanation for this, we hypothesize that if a
438 downregulation of *yenR* had occurred following exposure to the orange extract this might
439 have taken place at earlier stages of the bacterial cell growth and that the posterior induction
440 seen at 24 h may be a counteracting response of the bacteria.

441 We next sought to determine whether treatment with the orange extract or naringin
442 influenced the expression of *flhDC*, *fliA* and *fleB*. These three genes are all members of the
443 flagellar transcriptional hierarchy in *Y. enterocolitica* and have been reported to be involved
444 in bacterial motility and biofilm formation¹³. FlhDC is the master regulator of this flagellar
445 regulon encoded by the *flhDC* operon which is at the top of the hierarchical cascade and
446 affects the expression of other flagellar genes such as *fliA* and *fleB*²⁵. *FlhDC* expression in *Y.*
447 *enterocolitica* reaches maximum levels at 25 °C whereas is largely reduced at temperatures
448 above 25 °C³⁴. Also, in *Y. enterocolitica*, temperatures below 30 °C induce the coordinate
449 expression of the flagellin genes (*fliA* and *fleB*)². Concomitantly, we examined the expression
450 of *flhDC*, *fleB* and *fliA* at 25 °C. Other authors have reported a similar experimental design¹³.
451 Our data show that exposure of *Y. enterocolitica* to the orange extract or to naringin at 25 °C
452 was associated to a time-dependent upregulation of the transcription levels of *flhDC* as well as
453 to a general induction in the expression of the alternative sigma factor, *fliA*, at the three time
454 points tested. We also detected some small regulatory changes in the levels of the class III
455 flagelin gene, *fleB*. The transcriptional modulators of *flhDC* in *Y. enterocolitica* and their
456 impact on the regulation of flagellar genes are not yet well understood. Various regulatory
457 factors or mechanisms might contribute to the modulation of *flhDC* transcription in response
458 to environmental factors. Very recently, it has been reported that OmpR, a pleiotropic

459 transcription factor which responds to environmental signals, directly activates the expression
460 of *flhDC* in *Y. enterocolitica*³⁴. Importantly, the expression of *flhDC* also affects the
461 expression levels of non-flagellar genes, including genes involved in metabolism. Nutritional
462 conditions can also regulate the expression of the flagellar regulon and the presence of short
463 chain fatty acids (dietary derived compounds) in the growth medium was found to increase
464 *flhDC* expression in *Y. enterocolitica*³⁶. We may speculate that in the presence of the
465 flavanone-enriched orange extract or naringin in the media, the ompR regulator might activate
466 *flhDC* transcription. Further research into the regulatory role of OmpR on *flhDC* transcription
467 is needed in order to understand the response of *Y. enterocolitica* to environmental signals
468 such as exposure to natural anti-QS molecules.

469 The results presented here show that a natural orange extract enriched in flavanones
470 (mainly naringin, neohesperidin and hesperidin) at doses that can be achieved in the gut
471 through the diet exhibits a moderate antipathogenic activity against *Y. enterocolitica* by
472 reducing the production of *N*-acylhomoserine lactones and the formation of biofilm. These
473 responses were found to be associated to the induction of two important QS-regulatory genes,
474 *yenR* and *flhDC*. Other genes or alternative mechanisms, such as inhibition of the synthesis of
475 AHLs at the protein level, inhibition of the transport and secretion of AHLs to the media or
476 enzymatic degradation of AHLs might be involved in the observed responses. Many natural
477 extracts (fruits, herbs, spices) have been suggested to inhibit QS by a combination of
478 mechanisms²⁷. Like previously reported for naringenin²⁰, exogenous supply of the AHLs to
479 the culture media was not sufficient to compensate for the inhibitory effects induced by
480 naringin on motility and biofilm formation suggesting that other possible mechanisms such
481 antagonism of AHLs receptors or inhibition of targets down-stream AHL-receptor binding²⁷
482 may also be involved in the observed inhibitory effects. All these other possible mechanisms

483 need to be further investigated in order to clarify the anti-*QS* mechanisms of flavanones and
484 other similar natural compounds.

485

486

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- 603

604 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

605

606 **Figure 1.** Chemical structure of the major flavanones present in the orange extract: (1)
607 naringin, (2) neohesperidin and (3) hesperidin.

608

609 **Figure 2.** LC-MS/MS chromatograms of 3-oxo-C6-HSL and C6-HSL present in the
610 supernatant from *Y. enterocolitica* control cultures (A) and from cultures supplemented with
611 orange extract (B), naringin (C), neohesperidin (D) or hesperidin (E).

612

613 **Figure 3.** Percentage of inhibition of the production of 3-oxo-C6-HSL and C6-HSL by *Y.*
614 *enterocolitica* grown in LB broth supplemented with the orange extract, naringin,
615 neohesperidin or hesperidin. Values are indicated as the % of inhibition with respect to the
616 quantity of AHLs present in the control untreated cultures and are the mean \pm SD (displayed
617 as error bars) of three independent experiments (n=2 replicates per experiment). Bars labeled
618 with different letters indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$. Values are all significantly
619 different from untreated controls ($P < 0.05$).

620

621 **Figure 4.** Differential expression of A) *yenI* and B) *yenR* in *Y. enterocolitica* following
622 exposure to the orange extract (200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for 6, 14 and 24 h during bacterial growth at 30
623 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The relative change in expression in treated cells (ratio treated/control, T/C) was
624 calculated against control cells at the same time points. Dashed lines mark the minimum (0.7)
625 and maximum (1.3) ratio values estimated to be intrinsic variability. Values are the mean \pm
626 SD (displayed as error bars) of at least four independent experiments (n=3 replicates per
627 experiment). Significant differences (P values < 0.05) between time points are indicated.

628

629 **Figure 5.** Percentage of inhibition of biofilm formation by *Y. enterocolitica* treated with the
630 orange extract, naringin, neohesperidin or hesperidin for 24 h. Naringenin (95 µg/mL) and
631 cinnamaldehyde (50 µg/mL) were included as positive controls. Values are indicated as the %
632 of inhibition with respect to the control untreated cultures and are the mean ± SD (displayed
633 as error bars) of three independent experiments (n=2 replicates per experiment). Bars labeled
634 with different letters indicate significant differences at $P<0.05$. Values are all significantly
635 different from untreated controls ($P<0.05$).

636

637 **Figure 6.** Swimming motility in *Y. enterocolitica* (grown at 25 °C on 0.3% swim agar plates
638 which were point inoculated). Motility was determined by measuring the swimming diameter
639 (mm) in untreated (control) plates and plates treated with the orange extract (A) or naringin
640 (B) at 400 µg/mL for 24 h. Cinnamaldehyde (50 µg/mL) was included as a positive control.
641 Values are the mean ± SD (displayed as error bars) of at least four independent experiments
642 (n=3 replicates per experiment). Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) with control samples are
643 indicated.

644

645 **Figure 7.** Relative gene expression levels in *Y. enterocolitica* of *flhDC*, *fliA* and *fleB* at 25 °C
646 as a function of cell growth. Dashed lines mark the minimum (0.7) and maximum (1.3) ratio
647 values estimated to be intrinsic variability. Values are the mean ± SD (displayed as error bars)
648 of at least four independent experiments (n=3 replicates per experiment). Bars labeled with
649 different letters indicate significant differences against values at 6 h ($P<0.01$). Bacterial
650 growth is shown as absorbance at 600 nm and values are the mean ± SD (displayed as error
651 bars) of n=4 replicate wells.

652

653 **Figure 8.** Differential expression of *flhDC*, *fliA* and *fleB* in *Y.enterocolitica* at 6, 14 and 24 h
654 of growth and 25 °C in the presence of A), C) and D) soluble orange extract (200 and 400
655 µg/mL) and B), D) and F) naringin (200 and 400 µg/mL).. Dashed lines mark the minimum
656 (0.7) and maximum (1.3) ratio values estimated to be intrinsic variability. Values are the
657 mean ± SD (displayed as error bars) of at least four independent experiments (n=3 replicates
658 per experiment). Significant differences (*P* values < 0.1 or <0.05) between time points are
659 indicated.

Table 1. Primers and Probes Used in the Study of Gene Expression in *Yersinia Enterocolitica*.

Gene	Product	Sequence Accession	Primers	Reporter (FAM)
<i>yenI</i>	N-acylhomoserine lactone synthase	YP_001005892.1	Forward primer: GATGTGAGCCTACCTATTGATGGTT Reverse primer: CCCACCATATCTCTTGCTAATGCTT	CCAGCCGATTCTTTG
<i>yenR</i>	Quorum-sensing transcriptional activator	AM286415.1	Forward primer: CCGGTTATATTGACGGCGAAAGATA Reverse primer: CGGCGGAATCCGTCGAT	CTGGGACGATAATTCC
<i>fliA</i>	RNA polymerase sigma factor for flagellar operon	AM286415.1	Forward primer: AACAAACGGCTCGGACGT Reverse primer: CTGGCGGTACTCAGTCAAATCAATA	AAGTCGCACAAAATC
<i>fleB</i>	Thermoregulated motility protein	L33468.1	Forward primer: GGC GGTCGAAAGATAATGAACAAAT Reverse primer: AGATTCCAGCCAGAACTTGCA	CCAATCGCCAATGCTG
<i>flhDC</i>	Motility master regulatory operon	AF081587.1	Forward primer: GCGCGCTTGCAGATGTT Reverse primer: GCTGCCTCTCAGCTCTTTATAGA	TTGCGTCTCGCTTTCT
<i>16S</i>	16R ribosomal RNA	AM286415.1	Forward primer: GCCCCCTGGACAAAGACT Reverse primer: GTGGACTACCAGGGTATCTAATCCT	TCCCCACGCTTTCG

Table 2. Percentage of Inhibition of the Violacein Produced by *C. violaceum* 494 Grown in LB Broth Supplemented with Three Different Concentrations of the Orange Extract or Each Individual Flavanone for 24 H.

Concentration	Inhibition %	Inhibition %	Inhibition %	Inhibition%
	Orange extract	Naringin	Neohesperidin	Hesperidin
100 µg/mL	12.85 ± 6.43 ^a	6.74 ± 1.83	10.50 ± 0.59	5.04 ± 4.14
200 µg/mL	22.79 ± 3.69	20.11 ± 8.49	13.20 ± 0.66	8.79 ± 3.83
400 µg/mL	29.70 ± 6.83	19.95 ± 6.43	18.95 ± 2.64	9.34 ± 9.92

^a: Results are all the mean ± SD of three independent experiments (n=2 replicates per experiment). Values are all significantly different from untreated controls ($P < 0.05$).

Table 3. Growth Kinetic Parameters of *Yersinia Enterocolitica* Grown at 30 °c in the Absence (Control) and Presence of the Orange Extract or Naringin. Values are Presented as the Mean \pm SD (n = 3).

Maximum specific growth rate (h ⁻¹)				
	A ^a	μ_{\max}^b	λ^c (h)	R ^{2d}
Control	0.30 \pm 0.04	0.02 \pm 0.02	12.08 \pm 2.67	0.99
Orange Extract				
100 μ g/mL	0.33 \pm 0.06	0.02 \pm 0.01	12.20 \pm 2.41	0.98
200 μ g/mL	0.34 \pm 0.07	0.02 \pm 0.00	11.27 \pm 4.08	0.98
400 μ g/mL	0.29 \pm 0.04	0.02 \pm 0.00	14.29 \pm 0.27	1.00
Naringin				
100 μ g/mL	0.36 \pm 0.02	0.02 \pm 0.01	10.16 \pm 0.47	0.98
200 μ g/mL	0.36 \pm 0.00	0.02 \pm 0.01	11.69 \pm 2.37	0.99
400 μ g/mL	0.32 \pm 0.04	0.02 \pm 0.01	11.82 \pm 2.15	0.98

^a: maximum absorbance value at the stationary phase; ^b: maximum specific growth; ^c: lag phase duration in hours. ^d: coefficient of determination.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

TOC GRAPHICS

An Orange Extract Rich in Glycosylated Flavanones Moderately Inhibits *Quorum Sensing (QS)* in *Yersinia enterocolitica* by Reducing *N*-Acylhomoserine Lactones Production and Biofilm Formation

